

Bias and Entropy Part III

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In Part II, we suggested that given a gas with N particles and total energy E , there is necessarily a bias associated with e_i , single particle energy. Thus, $f(e_i)$ is not a constant. We suggested that one consider a gas with $N \rightarrow$ infinite particles and draw out $N_1 \rightarrow$ infinite, but $N_1 \ll N$, particles one at a time. This process experimentally yields the distribution $f(e_i)$. If the bias is only due to e_i , then e_i is the only information represented by $f(e_i)$. In such a case, $e_i + e_j = E_1$ for any i, j pair and $f(e_i)f(e_j) = \text{Constant}(E_1)$ in order that the bias only exists at the e_i level. The experimental process, however, may indicate that $f(e_i)f(e_j) \neq \text{constant}(E_1)$ in which case there is extra bias in the problem, beyond e_i . This suggests the particles are not independent and this may be directly linked to their interactions.

It is possible, however, that there exists an $G(f(e_i))$ such that this quantity is only linked to the bias e_i , i.e. $G(f(e_i))G(f(e_j)) = C(e_i + e_j)$. Such a consideration leads to Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein statistics.

Lack of Bias

We suggested in Part II that one seeks to remove bias in statistical systems. Given N particles with total energy E , there is necessarily a bias associated with the constraint E , i.e. each particle is linked with the information e_i . In other words, there exists a function $F(f(e_i))$ such that:

$$F(f(e_i)) = e_i \quad \text{and} \quad F(f(e_i)f(e_j)) = e_i + e_j \quad ((1)) \quad \text{for independence and only } e_i \text{ bias}$$

Each $f(e_i)$ only contains information about e_i and there is complete independence of particles so $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ should equal the unnormalized probability $f(e_i + e_j)$. Thus: $\text{constant} * F = \ln$. This is the usual Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

In Part II, we considered the experiment of collecting particles, one at a time, from a gas with N , E . N_1 particles are collected, such that N_1 is very large, but $N_1 \ll N$. If the particles are only biased based on e_i , there should exist a function ((1)).

If one considers permutations of the trial run N_1 , then the number of permutations is:

$$\# \text{permutations} = N! / \text{Product } i \ n(e_i)! \quad \text{Where } n(e_i) = N f(e_i) \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{where } \sum \text{over } i \ e_i f(e_i) = E/N \quad ((3))$$

One needs a large N_1 to ensure independence of $n(e_i)$. In such a case:

$$\ln(\# \text{permutations}) = \sum \text{over } i \ \ln(n(e_i)!) + \text{constants} \quad ((4))$$

One has two equations ((3)) and ((4)) with independent $f(e_i)$ terms. If e_i is the only information in the problem, these two equations should not be independent, i.e one should be a constant multiplied by the other. This holds at the level of each e_i term due to independence, thus:

$$\ln(n(e_i)!) = e_i f(e_i) \quad ((5))$$

Using Stirling's approximation yields: $n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) = \text{Constant } e_i n(e_i)$ which in turn yields:

$$n(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \text{ for constant } = -1/T \quad ((6))$$

Thus, one obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann result without a maximization process (i.e. maximization of entropy), although mathematically one may maximize: $-n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i))$ subject to the constraint $1/T \sum e_i n(e_i)$ to obtain the same result.

:It is possible, however, that e_i is not the only bias in the problem. There may be physical considerations which yield further biases. In such a case, the experiment of drawing out one particle at a time will show that $f(e_i)f(e_j) \neq C(E_1)$ for $e_i+e_j=E_1$. In other words, there is something special about $f(e_i)$ other than e_i .

In such a case, if one considers: $F(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, then:

$$(e_i+e_j) (-1/T) = F(f(e_i)) + F(f(e_j)) = \ln([\ln \text{ inverse } F(f(e_i))] [\ln \text{ inverse } F(f(e_j))]) \text{ where } F \text{ is no longer } \ln. \quad ((7))$$

The form of F must be linked to the extra physical bias in the problem. One needs this extra bias information to proceed.

Consider the case of Fermi-Dirac scattering. In general, only one particle may exist in an energy level at a point. Thus, e_1 cannot scatter into e_2 at a point if e_2 is occupied at the same spatial point. There is an interaction bias, linked with $f(e_i)$, which is not simply an energy bias. In terms of $f(e_i)$, there is a hindrance factor of:

$$1 - f(e_i) \quad ((8)) \text{ on average for scattering into } e_i.$$

If one is able to construct a function of $f(e_i)$ such that it becomes unbiased, then one may argue that e_i becomes the only bias in the problem. In other words, the scattering bias becomes incorporated into this function. Given ((8)), one may write:

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) [1-f(e_3)] [1-f(e_4)] = f(e_3)f(e_4) [1-f(e_1)][1-f(e_2)] \quad ((9))$$

This leads to: $G(f(e_i)) = f(e_i) / [1 - f(e_i)] \quad ((10))$ as being a function which is unbiased in scattering because:

$$G(f(e_i)) G(f(e_j)) = C(e_i+e_j) \quad ((10)) \text{ where } C \text{ is a constant}$$

In such a case, $e_i + e_j = E$ and $\ln(G(f(e_i)f(e_j))) = \ln(G(f(e_i))) + \ln(G(f(e_j)))$ cannot be independent equations. They must be equivalent if one is multiplied by a constant, say $-1/T$. Thus:

$$-e/T + c_1 = \ln(G(f(e))) = \ln(f(e)/(1-f(e))) \text{ which leads to the Fermi-Dirac result } ((11))$$

A similar result holds for the Bose-Einstein case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, e_i may not be the only bias in a gas of N particles with total energy E . There may be further biases due to physical scattering constraints. If, however, one may incorporate such a bias into a function of $f(e_i)$, this function behaves as an independent entity like e_i and so the only bias remaining is e_i . An equation involving this $G(f(e_i))$ must be a constant multiplied by e_i , e.g. $-e_i/T$. A scattering scenario provides such a scenario because an elastic interaction brings in the equation: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$, but one now also has: $G(f(e_1))G(f(e_2)) = G(f(e_3))G(f(e_4))$ and so if there is no extra bias other than e_i , then $\ln(G(f(e_i))) = -1/T e_i + \text{constant}$, which leads to the Fermi-Dirac distribution. A similar result holds for the Bose-Einstein case. In other words, one does not formally need to use the maximization of an entropy function subject to a constraint, but may obtain results based on the idea of bias.